

Comprehensive Evaluation of Syncope in Outpatient Clinics

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ABSTRACT

Syncope is a prevalent medical issue frequently encountered in outpatient healthcare settings, notable for its multifarious etiologies and diverse pathophysiological underpinnings. Establishing a rigorous, standardized approach guided by clinical guidelines is imperative to expedite the diagnosis of rare yet perilous conditions. This article underscores the critical importance of a systematic and thorough syncope evaluation process, emphasizing the pivotal role it plays in optimizing clinical outcomes and safeguarding patient well-being.

Keywords: Syncope; Evaluation; Management; Outpatient; Emergency clinic

INTRODUCTION

Syncope, commonly denoted as "unexplained collapse," presents a prevalent challenge encountered within the sphere of acute outpatient clinics. The reported prevalence of this phenomenon escalates to 41%, with recurrent syncope afflicting up to 13.5% of the populace. Noteworthy gender disparities are evident, with males exhibiting a diminished prevalence of 15% in contrast to the 22% prevalence observed in females^[1].

Syncope, by definition, is marked by an abrupt, transient, and complete loss of consciousness (LOC) that ensues from a state of global cerebral hypoperfusion. Typically, this incapacitating episode is succeeded by an expeditious and spontaneous recovery within a time limit ranging from mere seconds to less than three minutes^[2]. Throughout the episode, individuals experiencing LOC are devoid of self-awareness and are unresponsive to external stimuli^[2]. Syncope represents the primary concern in a notable 70-80% of cases managed within outpatient clinics^[3].

Conversely, the realm of Presyncope, which encompasses entities colloquially referred to as Mimic, Pseudo, and Near Syncope, entails a broader spectrum of episodes that mimic syncope but do not culminate in a complete loss of consciousness. Presyncope is notably distinguished by the presence of prodromal symptoms, including sensations of dizziness, unsteadiness, visual or auditory disturbances, nausea, diaphoresis, and a pervasive sense of coldness. Crucially, it does not progress to actual LOC^[2,3]. The prevalence of Presyncope within outpatient clinics is estimated to comprise a substantial proportion, ranging from 20% to 30%^[2,3].

Clinical Types of Syncope

The etiology of syncope and presyncope encompasses a broad spectrum of underlying factors necessitating a comprehensive evaluation for accurate identification and subsequent management. The following categorization highlights the diverse causative factors^[2-8]:

1. **Neurally Mediated (Reflex) Syncope (NMS):**

Neurally mediated syncope accounts for the majority, approximately 45%, of cases and follows a benign course. Its pathophysiology involves complex interactions within the autonomic nervous system, favoring paradoxical parasympathetic or vagal tone. This results in bradycardia, hypotension, peripheral vasodilation (evidenced by warm extremities), and transient cerebral hypoperfusion. Clinical manifestations encompass diaphoresis, dizziness, nausea, a sensation of warmth, pallor, sweaty palms, blurred vision, culminating in syncope or near-syncope. Absence of cardiac disease, long history of recurrent syncope. After some characteristics trigger factors.

NMS further subdivides into:

A. Vasovagal Syncope (VVS):

Specific triggers include intense emotions (such as stress or fear), excessive heat exposure, noxious stimuli, severe pain, prolonged standing, witnessing blood or needles, prolonged physical exertion, and dehydration or skipping meals.

B. Situational Syncope:

Specific triggers encompass vigorous coughing, laughter, urination, defecation, swallowing, gastrointestinal stimulation, eating, and may occur post-exercise or during meals.

C. Carotid Sinus Hypersensitivity (CSH):

Specific triggers include head rotation, circumferential neck compression, pressure on the carotid sinus, and shaving.

2. Orthostatic Hypotension (OH):

This condition involves a significant drop in systolic BP (≥ 20 mm Hg) or diastolic BP (≥ 10 mm Hg) upon assuming an upright posture (upon standing). It is frequently attributed to autonomic dysfunction, dehydration, or medication use. Its incidence is approximately 10%. Subtypes of orthostatic hypotension include:

A. Drug-Induced (Medication):

Specific triggers involve the initiation or alteration of drug dosage, including alcohol, antianginal agents, antidepressants, antidiabetic agents, antihypertensives, antiparkinsonian agents, diuretics, flibanserin (Addyi), and insulin.

B. Postural Tachycardia Syndrome (PTS):

This syndrome affects young adults, primarily females, and is often associated with chronic fatigue syndrome and mitral valve prolapse. It manifests as severe orthostatic intolerance accompanied by marked tachycardia.

C. Primary Autonomic Failure:

Conditions such as multiple sclerosis, multiple system atrophy (e.g., Shy-Drager syndrome), Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism, and Wernicke encephalopathy present with orthostatic hypotension upon postural changes.

D. Secondary Autonomic Failure:

Disorders like amyloidosis, chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy, connective tissue diseases, diabetes mellitus, Lewy body dementia, advanced age, spinal cord injury, and uremia result in orthostatic hypotension upon postural change.

E. Volume Depletion:

Clinical presentation includes hypotension, tachycardia, and dehydration, often resulting from conditions such as acute significant blood loss (e.g., gastrointestinal bleeding, ectopic pregnancy), trauma with substantial blood loss (e.g., tissue rupture, aortic aneurysm, spleen injury or rupture), and severe diarrhea or vomiting leading to inadequate fluid intake (e.g., acute gastroenteritis).

3. Cardiac Syncope:

Cardiac syncope accounts for approximately 20% of syncope presentations, primarily attributed to arrhythmias, with structural cardiac abnormalities less frequently implicated. Presence of definite structural heart disease Syncope during exertion Syncope while supine. Preceded by palpitation Family history of sudden death Long QT or Brugada pattern on ECG findings.

A. Arrhythmia (Irregular Heartbeat):

Clinical scenarios present abruptly and without provocation, often accompanied by palpitations. Features such as abnormal electrocardiographic findings, a family history of sudden death, personal history of heart disease, sudden onset of palpitations, and symptoms during or after exertion while in a supine or prone position warrant investigation. Specific arrhythmias include atrial fibrillation with Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome, atrial flutter, atrial surgery, AV block, AV canal defects, sinus node dysfunction, supraventricular tachycardia, ventricular tachycardia, pacemaker, or automated internal cardiac defibrillator dysfunction, Brugada syndrome, catecholaminergic tachycardia, and long QT syndrome.

B. Obstructive and Hypertrophic Cardiomyopathy (OCM- HCM):

These conditions are often asymptomatic but may lead to arrhythmias, chest pain, dyspnea, or syncope. Notably, dynamic systolic murmurs may intensify during squatting to standing or during the Valsalva maneuver.

C. Structural Heart Disease:

Various structural cardiac abnormalities contribute to syncope, including acute myocardial infarction or ischemia, arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy, infiltrative conditions (e.g., amyloidosis, hemochromatosis, sarcoidosis), valvular heart disease (e.g., aortic stenosis, mitral stenosis, pulmonary stenosis), acute aortic dissection, cardiac masses (e.g., atrial myxoma, cardiac tumors), cardiac tamponade, pulmonary hypertension, and saddle pulmonary embolus. The clinical manifestations and severity vary based on the specific condition.

Differential Diagnosis:

Differentiating non-syncopal syndromes is critical in clinical practice, particularly when patients experience sudden loss of consciousness (T-LOC) without an associated decrease in cerebral blood flow. Notable differential diagnoses include epilepsy, which presents with various seizure types, including absence seizures, tonic-clonic seizures, and complex partial seizures, all capable of inducing T-LOC^[9]. Psychogenic non-epileptic seizures (PNES) represent psychological episodes that mimic epileptic seizures and may involve T-LOC^[9]. Intoxication from drugs or alcohol can induce transient loss of consciousness or altered mental states^[9].

Metabolic disorders, such as hypoglycemia, can lead to T-LOC or altered consciousness^[9]. Conditions like hyperkalemia or hyponatremia can impact brain function, resulting in T-LOC^[9]. Hypoxic events, including those occurring during sleep apnea episodes, may result in transient loss of consciousness^[9]. Narcolepsy can involve sudden loss of muscle tone, known as cataplexy, leading to apparent T-LOC^[9]. In several disorders, consciousness is seemingly lost, as observed in "psychogenic pseudo-syncope," cataplexy, and drop attacks^[9].

Neurological disorders, such as complex partial seizures or transient global amnesia, can lead to T-LOC^[9]. Sleep disorders, including sleepwalking, night terrors, and REM sleep behavior disorder, may entail episodes of altered consciousness or complex behaviors during sleep^[9].

Individuals with migraines sometimes experience an aura phase characterized by neurological symptoms, including visual disturbances, and altered consciousness, without syncope^[9]. Hyperventilation syndrome, associated with rapid, shallow breathing, can result in symptoms like lightheadedness and confusion, resembling non-syncopal attacks^[9].

Certain medications, particularly those affecting the central nervous system, can induce drowsiness, confusion, or altered consciousness^[9]. Autoimmune disorders, such as multiple sclerosis or neuromyelitis optica, may lead to transient neurological symptoms, including altered consciousness^[9].

Transient ischemic attacks (TIAs) of carotid origin manifest with various focal symptoms, including sudden numbness or weakness of the face, arm, or leg, often accompanied by confusion, speech disorders, hemianopia, walking difficulties, dizziness, loss of balance, coordination, and severe unexplained headaches^[9,12].

Effective differentiation among these diverse causes of transient loss of consciousness is pivotal, as it informs tailored management and treatment strategies contingent on the underlying condition. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation by a healthcare professional is indispensable^[9,12].

9- Developed in collaboration with, European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA), Heart Failure Association (HFA), Heart Rhythm Society (HRS), External Contributors, Haruhiko Abe (Japan), David G. Benditt (USA), Wyatt W. Decker (USA), Blair P. Grubb (USA), Horacio Kaufmann⁹ (USA), Carlos Morillo (Canada), Brian Olshansky (USA), Steve W. Parry (UK), Robert Sheldon (Canada), Win K. Shen (USA). Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of syncope (version 2009) The Task Force for the Diagnosis and Management of Syncope of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). European Heart Journal. 2009 Nov 1;30(21):2631-71

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Initial Evaluation of Patients with Syncope:

The initial assessment of patients presenting with syncope is a critical and fundamental step in clinical practice, serving to address three key questions:

1. **Is it a syncopal episode or not?**
2. **Has the etiological diagnosis been determined?**
3. **Are there data suggestive of a high risk of cardiovascular events or death?**

The differentiation between syncope and non-syncopal conditions, whether involving genuine or apparent loss of consciousness (LOC), can typically be achieved through a detailed clinical history. However, it's essential to acknowledge that at times, this differentiation can pose substantial challenges.

To ascertain the nature of the episode, several critical questions must be addressed:

- **Was the loss of consciousness (LOC) complete?**
- **Was the LOC transient, characterized by rapid onset and short duration?**
- **Did the patient recover spontaneously, fully, and without any residual effects?**
- **Did the patient experience a loss of postural tone?**
-

Positive responses to these questions indicate a high likelihood of syncope, whereas negative responses necessitate the exclusion of other forms of LOC before proceeding with a syncope evaluation^[13-15].

The comprehensive evaluation of patients with syncope should be initiated with meticulous history-taking and an extensive general examination. This examination includes the measurement of blood pressure in both supine and standing positions, followed by the acquisition of an electrocardiogram (ECG)^[9]. The history-taking process should adopt a multifaceted approach, addressing various facets, including:

- **Prognosis assessment**
- **Diagnostic discernment**
- **Identification of reversible or ameliorable factors**
- **Evaluation of comorbidities**
- **Scrutiny of medication usage**
- **Consideration of patient and family requisites^[9].**
-

Following the initial assessment, risk stratification becomes imperative to categorize syncope cases into low, intermediate, and high-risk groups. This classification hinges on two critical elements:

- **The risk of death and life-threatening events**
- **The risk of syncope recurrence and physical injury^[9,10].**

Patients should receive personalized advice to prevent syncope recurrence. High-risk cases warrant referral to an acute care setting for admission, while intermediate-risk cases should be referred to secondary care based on suspected diagnoses. Notably, cardiac syncope carries a more severe prognosis compared to non-cardiac Neurally mediated syncope (NMS), and prognostic factors play a pivotal role in distinguishing between the two^[9,10].

The diagnostic aspect of the patient's history should delve into the circumstances surrounding syncope episodes, probing for prodromal symptoms that offer valuable physiological insights. This inquiry includes gathering self-reported information from the patient and collecting bystander observations of the syncope event. Vital signs and post-event symptoms must undergo meticulous scrutiny, and when available, video recordings can serve as valuable diagnostic aids^[9].

Furthermore, careful attention should be devoted to elucidating the temporal relationship between syncope episodes, meal intake, and physical activities. Additionally, the duration and characteristics of the prodrome can be instrumental in distinguishing between NMS and cardiac syncope^[11-12].

In older patients, an exhaustive investigation into comorbid conditions and medication usage is paramount. A comprehensive medical history, with a specific focus on the presence of preexisting cardiovascular ailments, must be diligently elicited. Additionally, it is imperative to solicit a detailed family history, emphasizing any instances of syncope or sudden unexplained deaths, including drownings, within the familial context^[11-12].

Considering these historical characteristics in the evaluation of patients with syncope can aid in differentiating between cardiac and non-cardiac causes, which, in turn, informs prognosis, aids in diagnosis, and guides the development of tailored treatment plans^[11-12].

The subsequent step in patient evaluation involves a comprehensive physical examination, which follows an ABC approach, particularly crucial in cases of life-threatening conditions such as pulmonary embolism, acute myocardial infarction, fatal arrhythmias, acute aortic dissection, and seizures. This examination aims to identify vital signs indicative of specific conditions^[13], including:

1. **Acute Hypoxia:** Particularly crucial in cases of massive pulmonary embolism.
2. **Heart Rhythm Abnormalities:** Indicated by assessing heart rhythm.
3. **Orthostatic Hypotension:** Evaluated through postural blood pressure measurements.
4. **Blood Pressure Discrepancy in Both Arms:** A potential sign of acute aortic dissection.

Following this initial assessment, a comprehensive cardiorespiratory examination is performed to diagnose various potential causes of syncope, such as cardiac failure, structural valvular disease, or aortic stenosis^[13]. Subsequently, a complete neurological examination is conducted to detect any significant focal deficits or other abnormalities that may require further in-depth neurological evaluation or appropriate referrals^[13].

Furthermore, syncope patients are examined for any potential injuries resulting from the syncopal episode^[14,15].

The comprehensive physical examination mandates meticulous assessment, including determining orthostatic blood pressure and heart rate fluctuations. This evaluation encompasses measurements in both the recumbent (lying) and seated positions, immediate assessment upon standing, and subsequent monitoring after three minutes in an upright posture. Particular attention is paid to heart rate and rhythm, and auscultation is performed to detect any murmurs, gallops, or rubs that may indicate underlying structural heart pathology^[9].

Notably, life-threatening syncope carries a mortality rate of 10% within six months, escalating to 30% in untreated cases. The implementation of standardized syncope guidelines serves as a crucial step toward enhancing both the diagnosis and management of syncope, thereby mitigating unnecessary admissions, and reducing overall healthcare costs^[9-15].

When applied rigorously, these guidelines identify only 12% of cases as cardiac events necessitating further comprehensive investigation^[9-15].

In evaluating patients with syncope, considering these historical characteristics can help differentiate between cardiac and non-cardiac causes, aiding in prognosis, diagnosis, and treatment planning (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Historical Characteristics of Cardiac and Noncardiac Causes of Syncope in Comparison to High/Low-Risk Stratification^[16]

Characteristic	More Often Associated with Cardiac Causes of Syncope	More Often Associated with Noncardiac Causes of Syncope
Age	- Older age (>60 years)	- Younger age (<50 years)
Gender	- Male sex	- No sex differences
Cardiac History	- Known ischemic heart disease - Structural heart disease - Previous arrhythmias - Reduced ventricular function	- No known cardiac disease
Prodromal Symptoms	- Brief prodrome (e.g., palpitations) or sudden loss of consciousness without prodrome	- Presence of prodrome (e.g., nausea, vomiting, feeling warmth)
Activity During Syncope	- Syncope during exertion	- Syncope only in the standing position, or situational

Characteristic	More Often Associated with Cardiac Causes of Syncope	More Often Associated with Noncardiac Causes of Syncope
Body Position During Syncope	- Syncope in the supine position	- Positional change from supine or sitting to standing
Frequency of Syncope Episodes	- Low number of syncope episodes (1 or 2)	- Frequent recurrence and prolonged history of syncope with similar characteristics
Cardiac Examination Findings	- Abnormal cardiac examination (e.g., murmurs, gallops, or rubs indicating structural heart disease)	-Normal cardiovascular examination, except for bradycardia and hypotension.
Family History	- Family history of inheritable conditions or premature Sudden Cardiac Death (≥ 50 years)	- Negative family history
Congenital Heart Disease	- Presence of known congenital heart disease	- Absence of congenital heart disease
Triggers	- The most important trigger is after exercise	- Presence of specific triggers (e.g., dehydration, pain, distressful stimulus, medical environment) -Situational triggers (e.g., cough, laugh, micturition, defecation, deglutition)
ECG changes	-ECG changes suggestive of arrhythmic syncope (e.g., bifascicular block, sinus bradycardia < 40 beats per minute in absence of sinoatrial block or medication use, QRS preexcitation, abnormal QT interval, ST-segment elevation leads V1 through V3 [Brugada pattern], negative T wave	-Normal ECG finding

Characteristic	More Often Associated with Cardiac Causes of Syncope	More Often Associated with Noncardiac Causes of Syncope
	in right precordial leads and epsilon wave [arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia/ cardiomyopathy])	
Risk Stratification	High-Risk Stratification	Low-Risk Stratification

Risk Stratification of Patients Presenting with Syncope

Risk stratification assessment in syncope plays a pivotal role in guiding clinical management and decision-making. It involves categorizing patients into different risk groups to determine the appropriate level of evaluation, treatment, and follow-up. Several factors are considered in this process:

1. **Clinical Prediction Rules:** Clinical prediction rules, such as the San Francisco Syncope Rule and the Boston Syncope Criteria, are valuable tools for risk stratification in syncope. They incorporate various clinical parameters, including patient history and examination findings, to identify low-risk individuals who may not require extensive testing or hospitalization^[17,18].
 The Boston Syncope Criteria can be categorized as follows:
 - 1) Signs and symptoms of an acute coronary syndrome (ACS)
 - 2) Signs of conduction disease
 - 3) Worrisome cardiac history
 - 4) Valvular heart disease by history or physical examination
 - 5) Family history of sudden death
 - 6) Persistent abnormal vital signs in the ED
 - 7) Volume depletion such as persistent dehydration, gastrointestinal bleeding, or he
 - 8) Primary CNS (central nervous system) event

While the San Francisco Syncope Rule can be categorized as a “CHESS” mnemonic

C: History of Congestive heart failure

H: Hematocrit <30%

E: abnormal ECG

S: a patient complaint of Shortness of breath, and

S: a triage Systolic blood pressure <90 mm Hg)

2. **Abnormal Electrocardiogram (ECG) Findings:** ECG findings can significantly influence risk stratification. Abnormal ECG patterns, such as ventricular arrhythmias, heart block, or evidence of ischemia, are associated with a higher risk of adverse outcomes and may prompt more aggressive evaluation and management^[19].
3. **Structural Heart Disease:** The presence of structural heart disease, assessed through echocardiography or other imaging modalities, is an important determinant of risk. Conditions like hypertrophic cardiomyopathy or significant valvular disease can increase the risk of syncope-related complications^[20].
4. **Syncope Type:** The underlying cause or type of syncope can impact risk stratification. For instance, vasovagal syncope is generally considered low risk, while syncope due to arrhythmias or structural heart abnormalities carries a higher risk^[21].
5. **Age and Comorbidities:** Age and the presence of comorbidities, such as diabetes or hypertension, can influence risk assessment. Older adults and those with multiple comorbid conditions may be at higher risk for adverse outcomes following syncope episodes^[22].
6. **Medication Use:** Certain medications, such as antiarrhythmics or anticoagulants, can affect the risk of adverse events in patients with syncope. Evaluating medication profiles is essential in risk assessment^[23].
7. **Syncope Recurrence:** Patients with recurrent syncope may be at higher risk of adverse outcomes and should be closely monitored and evaluated to identify underlying causes and prevent recurrence^[24].
8. **Evaluation of Orthostatic Hypotension:** Assessing blood pressure changes with positional changes (orthostatic vital signs) is crucial. The presence of orthostatic hypotension can signal autonomic dysfunction and impact risk stratification^[25].
9. **Evaluation of Cardiac Biomarkers:** In some cases, measuring cardiac biomarkers, such as troponin and B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP), can provide additional information for risk stratification, especially in cases where myocardial ischemia or heart failure is suspected^[26].
10. **Syncope Units and Specialized Evaluation:** Some centers have established syncope units where specialized evaluation and risk stratification can be conducted, often involving neuroimaging, electrophysiological studies, and tilt-table testing^[27].

In summary, risk stratification in syncope is a multifaceted process that considers various clinical, electrocardiographic, demographic, and diagnostic factors. It aims to categorize patients into risk groups to guide appropriate management strategies and optimize patient outcomes.

References:

Serious medical conditions necessitate careful consideration and evaluation to distinguish cardiac arrhythmias from intrinsic cardiac or vascular non-arrhythmic conditions or significant non-cardiac ailments (Table 2)

Table 2: Further Examples of Serious Medical Conditions That Might Need Warrant Consideration of Evaluation and Therapy in a Hospital Setting^[28].

Cardiac Arrhythmic	Conditions Cardiac or Vascular Nonrhythmic Conditions	Noncardiac Conditions
Amiodarone toxicity Bradyarrhythmia with sinus pauses or high-grade conduction block; Ventricular tachyarrhythmia Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome Brugada syndrome long-QT syndrome (LQTS) Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) Arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy (ARVC) Ventricular tachycardia Bundle branch block (QRS duration ≥ 120 ms) Sinoatrial block Atrioventricular block Sinus bradycardia (in physically untrained) Short-or long-QT intervals Brugada syndrome (right bundle branch block with ST-elevation in lead V1–V3) Negative T wave in right precordial leads and epsilon waves arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia Supraventricular tachycardia Bradyarrhythmias Moderate Sinus node disease	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Acute coronary syndrome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Significant hemorrhage -Trauma with significant blood loss -Gastrointestinal bleeding -Tissue rupture (e.g., severe bleeding from rupture aortic aneurysm, spleen injury, rupture ovarian cyst, ectopic pregnancy, and retroperitoneal hemorrhage)

2nd- or 3rd-degree heart block Pacemaker malfunction Drug-induced Tachyarrhythmias Severe Ventricular tachycardia Torsades de pointes Supraventricular tachycardia Drug- induced		
1- Pre-excitation syndromes (PR interval < 120 msec) with or without delta wave A- Wolf-Parkinson-White Syndrome (WPW) may have Atrioventricular Nodal Reentrant Tachycardia (AVNRT) or Atrial Fibrillation (AF) / Atrial Flutter (AFL) B- Lown- Ganong- Levine syndrome (LGL)		
2- Atrial fibrillation or Atrial Flutter	•Severe aortic valve stenosis	•Major traumatic injury due to syncope
3- Paroxysmal or Sustained Dysrhythmia • Non-Sinus rhythm of any sort • Nonspecific intraventricular conduction delay (QRS > 100 ms without left or right bundle branch pattern) • Left bundle branch block or left anterior or posterior hemiblock • ECG signs of coronary ischemia	•Cardiac tamponade	•Persistent abnormal vital sign

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long QT syndrome - QTc > 440-450 msec in men or > 460 msec in women • Brugada sign - right bundle branch block and anterior ST elevation • Left ventricular hypertrophy in someone with no reason to have it and/or Q waves in II, III, aVF, V5, and V6 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AV block (Mobitz type 2 and third heart block) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertrophic cardiac myopathy (HCM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pulmonary embolism -Saddle embolus resulting in outflow tract obstruction or severe hypoxia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sinus node dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Severe prosthetic valve dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cerebrovascular disease -Subarachnoid hemorrhage -Vascular steal syndromes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supraventricular tachycardia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pulmonary embolism 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ventricular tachycardia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aortic dissection 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pacemaker or automated internal cardiac defibrillator dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acute HF 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brugada syndrome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate-to-severe LV dysfunction 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catecholaminergic tachycardia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atrial myxomas 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long QT syndrome 		

Standard A 12 lead ECG should be performed in all patients with syncope attack to rule out bradyarrhythmia or tachyarrhythmias cardiac causes of syncope^[28,29].

Figure 1: WPW

- The presence of short PR intervals (< 12 mm)
- The presence of Delta waves.
- The presence of the widening of the QRS complexes as Ventricular pre-excitation syndromes

Figure 2: Lown- Ganong- Levine syndrome (LGLS)

- The presence of short PR intervals (<12mm)
- no Delta waves
- no widening of the QRS complexes
- The presence of clinical tachycardia

Figure 3: Atrial Fibrillation

- No visible P waves
- Irregularly irregular R-R interval
- Presence of narrow QRS complex

Figure 4: Atrial Flutter

- Regular atrial activity at ~300 bpm
- “Saw-tooth” pattern of inverted flutter waves in leads II, III, aVF
- Upright flutter waves in V1 that may resemble P waves
- The ventricular rate depends on the AV conduction ratio (4:1 Block)

Figure 5: WPW with Atrioventricular Nodal Reentry Tachycardia (AVNRT)

- Narrow complex AV nodal reentry tachycardia (180 bpm) suggestive of AVNRT
- With a short RP interval <120 msec.)
- The P waves can be seen immediately following the QRS complex (arrows).

Figure 6: Atrial Fibrillation with WPW

- Rapid, irregular, broad complex tachycardia (overall rate ~ 200 bpm).

- Subtle beat-to-beat variation in the QRS width which is more typical of WPW
- Presence of delta wave on the QRS
- This could easily be mistaken for AF with LBBB because of the dominant S wave in V1; it is not typical of LBBB, and the rate is too rapid for LBBB (up to 300 bpm in places, i.e. too rapid to be conducted via the AV node), and LBBB usually has fixed width QRS complexes.

Figure 7: Sick Sinus Syndrome

Sick Sinus Syndrome

- It showed bradycardia and pause and tachycardia

Figure 8: Second Heart Block (Mobitz Type 2)

Figure 9: Third Heart Block

Figure 10: Long QT Syndrome (LQTS)

Figure 11: Types of Brugada Syndrome

Figure 12: Hypertrophic Cardiomyopathy (HCM)

- Big giant voltage in chest lead with needle-like S- wave, with T wave inversion

Figure 13: Arrhythmogenic Right Ventricular Dysplasia (ARVC)

- Epsilon wave along with T-wave inversions, are seen in V1-V3

Figure 14: Myocardial Infarction (Transmural) (STEMI)

- Cardiac ischemia with ST-Segment Elevation

Figure 15: Subendocardial Ischemia

- Cardiac Ischemia with ST-segment depressions in the lateral leads

Figure 16: Ventricular Tachycardia

Figure 17: Supraventricular Tachycardia

Figure 18: Multifocal Atrial Tachycardia

Figure 19: Pulmonary Emboli

- S1 Q3 T3 pattern

Figure 20: Pericardial Effusion or Tamponed

- with low QRS voltage

Doing general laboratory tests to diagnose common causes of syncope (e.g., hemoglobin, sugar, lower GFR, cardiac enzymes) to detect metabolic abnormalities such as hypoglycemia, electrolyte imbalance, and acute drop in hemoglobin suggests blood loss^[17].

CONCLUSION

There is a high incidence rate of syncope in the outpatient clinics. There is a lack of standardized guidelines to approach syncope patients. Transient loss of consciousness with rapidly regaining consciousness is due to transient global cerebral hypoperfusion. A thorough history and examination can rule out life-threatening conditions. If the cause of syncope is undetermined after the initial evaluation, the physician should do risk stratified. The high-risk patient needs further assessment in the hospital. The standardized approach or pathway will reduce costs by reducing hospitalization, inappropriate investigations, and length of stay.

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